

MAIN DIFFERENCES BETWEEN AN UNDERSTANDING OF THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE OF A NATIVE SPEAKER AND A NON-NATIVE SPEAKER

Ibragimova Dildora Shamsiddinovna

Associate professor, Samarkand State Architectural And Construction University.

E-mail: dildoraibragimova1981@gmail.com

Abstract: Native speakers and non-native speakers understand a language differently. Native speakers have a better potential in learning of a language, but non-native speakers use a more formal language.

Keywords: Grammar, language, native speakers, non-native speakers, understand (understanding), vocabulary.

Introduction

The present study discusses the results of a case study conducted to explore how students perceive the advantages and disadvantages of having native and non-native English language teachers. The study also reports native and non-native teachers perception of their own teaching qualities as well as employers' perception of both groups through student feedback. Responding to the questionnaires and structured interviews, students named the following as their native teachers' advantages: teaching ability, grammaticality and idiomaticity, use of the standard English language accent, and their competence in dealing with spontaneous responses in the classroom. Non-native teachers, on the other hand, were perceived as role models, empathetic, better culturally aware and capable of delivering efficient instructions. A small number of the students were less satisfied with non-native teachers' command of the English language teaching in different social contexts. The results will be beneficial for native and non-native teachers in terms of realizing their strengths and weaknesses. Moreover, the results also reveal that native teachers are not always preferred by learners, despite their indisputable command of the target language. As speaking and writing skills are the part of communication skills, having proficiency in speaking is more needed in the modern world.

Every language teacher dreams of teaching effectively, of knowing that the lessons they're teaching daily are hitting their marks and helping their students master the language. Native and non-native speakers perceive both grammar and a vocabulary differently. Both have advantages and disadvantages. Native speakers live in a language speaking country or not. Some people learn a language mainly through a conversation, others – through films. They mostly do not use a dictionary and grammar books to understand the language. For them it is possible to understand grammar and words through an understanding of the situation, the intonation, the gestures etc. Although most of native speakers do not know the grammar rules, they use most of them. —We use the term —grammar with a systematic ambiguity. On the one hand, the term refers to explicit theory constructed by the linguist and proposed as a description of the speaker's competence. On the other hand, it refers to this competence itself. || A learning of grammar is not a basis for them, which let master a language. However, if they learn grammar they understand it better, than non-native speakers. Because, native speakers have a better feeling of language.

Native speakers use a vocabulary in an informal way. They use it for its main purpose – for a communication. Thus, an environment defines a vocabulary. A vocabulary of New York’s citizen differs from a vocabulary of a citizen of London a vocabulary of a truck driver differs from a vocabulary of an office worker. It is not only a slang, but also a set of particular words, which are used more, than others. In addition, most native speakers do not know the words, which are used in books, a complex vocabulary. Nevertheless, there are some native speakers, who know a lot of complex words. Native speakers have a potential to have a huge vocabulary. Nonnative speakers have less potential for this, because they might get a vocabulary of a 10-year-old child, who is a native speaker, only when they are 15 or 16. Non-native speakers perceive the language from a language environment or books, but they mostly use a dictionary and grammar books to understand it. They learn a language as an academic discipline

References

1. Chomsky, Noam and Halle, Morris – The Sound Pattern of English|| New York: Harper & Row, 1968, p 3-14.
2. Paul Nation – —4000 Essential English Words||, 1-6 books, Compass Publishing, 2009.
3. Shamsiddinova I. D. Teaching Foreign Languages in a Non-Linguistic University: Challenges and Strategies //Excellencia: International Multi-disciplinary Journal of Education (2994-9521). – 2024. – T. 2. – №. 4. – C. 259-262.
4. Shamsiddinova I. D., Kahramonova M. D., Kahramonova M. D. Teaching English to Defected Children //Academic Integrity and Lifelong Learning (France). – 2023. – C. 228-232.
5. Shamsiddinova I. D., Bakhtiyarova Z. N., Ulmaskulova S. U. Methods and strategies in teaching english
6. //European Journal of Molecular and Clinical Medicine. – 2020. – T. 7. – №. 3. – C. 4492-4496.